

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE LEVEL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF FOOD LEGISLATION AND THE FOOD SAFETY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN UKRAINE FOR THE DYNAMICS OF THE SPREAD OF FOOD POISONING (RETRO ANALYSIS)

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Abstract

Ensuring safe nutrition is one of the important tasks of each state for the proper state of public health. In developed countries such as the US and the EU, food safety is a public health priority and is ensured through the development of a regulatory framework, the establishment and implementation of effective food safety systems throughout the food chain. However, despite the existence of legislation and government oversight, official data show a high number of outbreaks of foodborne diseases in these countries. In this regard, WHO calls on states to constantly monitor the situation with the occurrence of food poisoning in order to improve the means of monitoring the safe nutrition of the population. In Ukraine, there is food legislation, which was formed much later than in the EU and the USA, and later the mechanism for ensuring safe food was introduced – the HACCP system (Hazard Analysis and Critical Control, English Point). The article presents retrospective analytical data related to the occurrence of food poisoning among the population of Ukraine in the pre-war period (2019–2020) and analyzes the problems that contributed to the emergence of these diseases. Comparison in dynamics allows to see not only the changes that have taken place, but also to understand the advantages and disadvantages that were applied in the previous period and develop measures based on the experience gained over the past years. The target issues of this article were the analysis of international and national food legislation as important tools for managing the level of food poisoning, a retro-analysis of the level of food poisoning in different regions of Ukraine and the establishment of factors that contributed to the occurrence of these diseases.

Keywords: food safety, food law, food poisoning, HACCP system.

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1. Introduction

Food safety is one of the important public health issues. Hazardous foods containing disease-causing bacteria, their toxins, viruses, parasites or harmful chemicals are responsible for

more than 200 different illnesses, from diarrhea to cancer. Serious consequences of diarrhea can be kidney and liver failure, brain and nerve disorders, rheumatoid arthritis, and death. Foodborne diseases not only negatively impact human health and well-being, but also have negative economic consequences for individuals, families, communities, businesses and countries. According to WHO estimates, 600 million people, and this is almost one in ten people in the world, get sick every year due to the use of poor-quality food. 420,000 people die every year from eating unsafe foods. This costs the global economy hundreds of billions of dollars. 40 % of foodborne illnesses occur in children under the age of five, with an average of 125,000 deaths. Consequently, the nutrition and health of the population cannot be improved without ensuring food safety [1–3].

According to the latest data from the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, about 1 in 6 Americans get sick each year due to eating unsafe foods, 128,000 are hospitalized, and 3,000 die each year from food-borne diseases. This is a significant burden on health care, which in most cases can be prevented. The operational strategy of the FDA (US Food and Drug Administration) is to strengthen the global food safety system and improve public health protection [4]. Food safety is an essential component of sustainable development and therefore of paramount importance to society as a whole. In the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by the UN for the period from 2015 to 2030, the issue of population nutrition is given a significant place, which states that by 2030 every person on the planet should have access to safe, nutritious food in sufficient volumes to meet their needs. The Sustainable Development Goals have 17 global goals, including the first three goals and goals 10, 12 on nutrition and nutrition-related health. For these purposes, it is emphasized that one of the important influences on a person is proper and safe nutrition, which ensures good health and well-being of the population. In recent decades, concern about food safety has especially increased worldwide on the part of public health authorities, the food industry and consumers, which has become the main impetus for the widespread use of the HACCP system. This concern has been confirmed by the significant increase in the incidence of foodborne illness in many countries in recent years. Thus, food safety around the world is a global problem, primarily for ensuring public health security and a serious problem for the development of each country [2, 5]. In Ukraine, the main driver of food safety is food legislation, which has a long way to its modern formation. The food legislation of Ukraine was formed on the basis of international requirements in this area and directly to the requirements of the EU food legislation.

The aim of this article is based on the analysis of literature data and our personal experience in the formation of normative documents of the legislative level, to provide a reasoned retrospective analysis of the formation of national food legislation in accordance with modern international requirements and to determine its regulatory significance in the field of the spread of food poisoning in Ukraine. To achieve this aim, the following tasks are set:

- conduct a retro-analysis of the historical path of the USA, the EU countries and Ukraine to create modern food legislation as the basis for ensuring food safety for the population;
- on the basis of a retrospective analysis of official data, determine the level of spread of food poisoning in different regions of Ukraine, including those caused by public catering, and to determine the causes that contributed to the emergence of these diseases;
- determine the features of the implementation (difficulties and negative aspects in the implementation) of HACCP food safety systems in public catering;
- identify key measures to improve the situation with the spread of food poisoning in Ukraine.

The number of national analytical scientific publications regarding information on the real state of foodborne diseases among the population of Ukraine is rather limited, and it is hoped that the conducted retro-analysis will contribute to the implementation of effective evidence-based preventive measures and decision-making to manage food risks in such a difficult time in Ukraine.

2. Materials and methods

Research materials: legislative and regulatory documents, sources of statistical data, scientific publications and electronic resources.

Research methods – retrospective analysis, descriptive, systematic analysis of literature data, retrospective-cohort, which were based on official statistics.

Legislative and regulatory documents includes: national food safety framework, EU and US food law.

Retrospective analysis is also subject to national government and regional reports, analytical articles on food poisoning.

Articles on food safety published by authors from different countries are qualitatively analyzed using a thematic analysis approach to identify the key concepts of the article. Articles published from 2000 to 2021 are used. The following databases are used: PubMed, Access Medicine, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, WHO Library, FAO Libraries.

The state of the spread of food poisoning in Ukraine is assessed for 2019 and 2020 by analyzing the national official annual reports on foodborne diseases registered in Ukraine.

Let's analyze the annual reports on the investigation of outbreaks and the spread of foodborne diseases of such national services that control food poisoning among the population: the State Food and Consumer Service and reports from its divisions, as well as reports from the Center for Public Health. Let's study the publicly available annual official summary of reported foodborne disease outbreaks in Ukraine from 2019 to 2020.

3. Research results and discussion

3. 1. Retro analysis of the historical way of creating modern international and national food legislation

3. 1. 1. Creation of modern international food law

National and international food safety legislation is being developed with the understanding that in a globalized world, food safety is a complex international policy issue that is at the intersection of agricultural policy, health policy and trade [3, 6, 7].

The American food safety system has played and is playing an important role in the world today. In the 60s of the last century in the United States, the food safety system (HACCP) was first introduced in the food industry, based on the concept of Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (in English, Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points) [8, 9]. Almost 20 years later, this HACCP system began to be actively used at the legislative level in the EU countries, and then also with almost the same time interval in Ukraine [10].

In the United States, food safety regulation is carried out at the state and federal levels. Food laws in the states are developed in accordance with federal laws. The main federal agencies responsible for food safety in the United States are the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the Food Inspection and Safety Service (FSIS) of the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA). The FDA regulates over 80 percent of the nation's food, while USDA-FSIS regulates meat, poultry, and processed eggs. As noted, the FDA and the HACCP system in the US have played a significant role in reducing foodborne illness, which has declined nearly 40 percent over the past 20 years. It should be noted that the food safety system in the United States is constantly being improved, since the number of diseases is still high [4]. In 2011, in the United States, in response to changes in the global food system and in connection with the widespread occurrence of foodborne diseases, the FDA approved the FSMA (Food Safety Modernization Act), which is recognized as a radical reform of US food safety laws. This law was introduced in 2018. The main goal of the law is to ensure food safety in the United States by shifting the focus of regulators on responding to cases of microbial contamination to the prevention of food poisoning. Under this new law, food manufacturers must apply the HACCP system. They must also formally endorse an approved risk assessment program. Following the United States, countries such as the United Kingdom and Canada, China, the United Arab Emirates, Egypt and others began to modernize their food safety rules [4, 11, 12].

The European food safety legal framework is currently considered one of the best in the world, and the European consumer is the most protected. In this regard, the EU food legislation is an example of a modern approach to ensuring food safety in the world and takes into account the interests of all those involved in the food market [13–15]. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) is a regulatory body that covers public health, food safety, animal health and protection, and plant health and protection [13–15].

The year 1993 can be considered the beginning of the modern food safety system. In this year, the fundamental Directive 93/43 EC on food hygiene was adopted in the EU. This Directive defines: general rules for food hygiene, food safety control methods, and establishes general requirements for all food businesses to apply the HACCP system.

However, each country in the EU has interpreted the Directive differently in their national regulations. Some EU countries have applied all of the HACCP principles, while others have applied only a few of them. Such inconsistencies between the laws and regulations of Member States created barriers to international trade and hampered the effectiveness of food safety in the domestic market.

As a consequence, in 2004 the European Parliament and the Council of the EU adopted Regulation EC 852/2004 “On the sanitary and hygienic rules for food production” (replacing Directive 93/43 EC), which defined uniform legal requirements for EU countries that should apply to all food industry enterprises to ensure food safety.

The foundations of modern European legislation were formed in 2002–2005. Regulation (EC) of the European Parliament and of the Council 178/2002 is considered fundamental, which had provisions for the creation of a single European regulatory body for food safety, established the principles of control “from link to table” and requirements for traceability in the food chain, as well as linguistic use procedures based on HACCP principles. In 2004, the “European Hygiene Pact” was developed, which included Regulations and Directives (EC): 854/2004; 882/2004: 91/496/EEC; 96/23/EC; 96/93/EC; 97/78/EC [13].

In 2017, Regulation 2017/625/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council introduced new food requirements to prevent, reduce or eliminate risks to human, animal and plant health. These requirements imply increased official control by the authorized bodies of food manufacturers. It is very important that this Regulation, from December 14, 2019, repeals a number of legislative acts that form the “European Hygiene Pact”: Regulation (EC) 854/2004, Regulation (EC) 882/2004, Directive 91/496/EEC, 23/EC, Directive 96/93/EC, Directive 97/78/EC, Decision 92/438/EEC [13].

Since the outbreak of COVID-19, many Member States have placed significant restrictions on the movement of their populations in order to protect public health. In this regard, the EU Commission adopted Regulation (EU) 2020/466 on the provisional measures necessary to contain the widespread risks to human, animal and plant health from food.

The basis for ensuring food safety in both the US and the EU is the HACCP system, where it is determined that this system is the best way to manage, but the approaches to its implementation in these countries should be noted. In EU countries, HACCP is mandatory at all stages of the food chain, except for primary production, while the use of HACCP in the US is less mandatory [12]. Despite the fact that the regulatory and institutional frameworks differ from country to country, international obligations are the same around the world and regulate the use of the HACCP system to ensure food safety. Foodborne illnesses can spread rapidly and cause health problems for people anywhere in the world. As a result of increased international trade, food produced in one country can be consumed in another part of the world and cause disease if contaminated with foodborne pathogens [1].

3. 1. 2. Creation of modern national food legislation

The history of the development of the food security strategy in Ukraine began with the preparation and approval of the Law of Ukraine “On Food Safety and Quality” in 1997 [6, 16–18]. In September 2015, the Law of Ukraine “On Food Safety and Quality” was harmonized with modern EU requirements and entered into force in a new edition and under a new name: “On the basic principles and requirements for food safety and quality.” The requirements of this law are aimed at ensuring food safety and consumer protection with the mandatory implementation of the HACCP system. From September 2019, this system must be in place at all enterprises in the food sector. For failure to comply with the obligation to implement the HACCP system, a fine is imposed on the operator of the food sector. Together with this updated Law, in 2017 Ukraine approved the Law “On State Control over Compliance with Legislation on Food, Feed, Animal By-Products, Animal Health and Welfare”.

The purpose of this Law is to harmonize the legislation of Ukraine on state control with the requirements of the EU, in accordance with the above-mentioned Regulations and Directives of the EU Council. This Law establishes the risk-oriented nature of state control, which is one of its important innovations [6, 19].

The legislation of Ukraine on food safety consists of the Constitution of Ukraine, the aforementioned Laws of Ukraine, as well as the Law of Ukraine “On information for consumers regarding food products” (2018), standards and other acts issued in accordance with the specified regulatory legal acts. Separately, it is necessary to note the Law of Ukraine “On information for consumers about food products”, which brings Ukrainian legislation closer to the provisions of EU Regulation No. 1169/2011 on providing consumers with information about food products and declares that the free movement of safe food products is an important aspect of the internal market to ensure the public health and welfare of citizens and the satisfaction of their social and economic interests.

Modern food legislation in Ukraine as a whole makes it possible to ensure food safety and protect the population from food risks.

In Ukraine, since 2016, state control over compliance with food legislation has been carried out by a single body, united from 4 departments – the State Service of Ukraine for Food Safety and Consumer Protection – the State Food and Consumer Service.

The Ukrainian food security system includes producers, processors, carriers, wholesale and retail trade, public catering and consumers. Responsibility for food safety lies with the manufacturer, but control is on the side of the state, within the framework of the functions of the State Food and Consumer Service. The government plays an important role in the formation of food legislation, sets standards and monitors their implementation. Educational and scientific institutions engaged in research and education are also involved in this process.

3. 2. HACCP system (Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point) and problems in its application in different countries of the world

The main guiding tool for food safety is the globally recognized HACCP system. Industry can benefit from the implementation of HACCP such as reduced waste, prevention of food poisoning, increased consumer confidence and complaints, and legal compliance. The HACCP system is gaining recognition and is now considered as a prerequisite for food manufacturers and a growing number of countries whose legislation requires the implementation of the system [5, 20–26].

Many scientific articles provide evidence why HACCP has certain barriers to implementation. The implementation of food safety systems in Lebanon is far below expectations and varies across time, geography and supply chains. Established four years after the implementation of the first food safety law, only (40 %) enterprises had a HACCP system.

In Slovakia, HACCP has been a legal obligation since 2001, but only 59 % of manufacturers in 2015 used the system. Weaknesses were found in the HACCP team members’ knowledge of hazard identification and errors in the hazard analysis process and the application of risk assessment methods. This was due to the fact that teams do not have proper guidance on exactly how to approach the application of the first principle of HACCP. Lack of understanding of HACCP by personnel is one of the main obstacles to its effective use [27–29].

Almost half of the managers of the surveyed enterprises in Turkey (46.5 %) reported that they did not really know what HACCP is [20]. Companies that independently developed the HACCP system in 82 % of cases had to change or correct it after a formal audit [29]. Problems in the implementation of HACCP are noted especially among small food producers, the most common problems in this are the cost of implementation, lack of economic resources, the complexity of the composition of food products, excessive paperwork, lack of motivation and control of staff. The greatest obstacle is the lack of knowledge of the staff and therefore training is an important tool to eliminate inconsistencies in the HACCP system and is a fundamental factor for success [5, 23, 24, 30, 31].

The largest food companies, equipped with significant resources, also experience difficulties in implementing the HACCP system [13, 24]. The above shows that despite the fact that the HACCP system is recognized worldwide as an effective tool in ensuring food safety, its implementation is not an easy procedure. An important negative factor is the lack of understanding

of the HACCP system by the management and personnel of food enterprises, the relatively high cost of developing and implementing this system, as well as the need to improve methodological guidelines for its application. [28, 29, 32, 33]. It should also be noted that in recent decades, many food safety schemes have emerged around the world. The most popular are public food safety management systems, such as ISO 22000 (FSMS, Food Safety Management System) and the HACCP system [26, 34, 35].

It has been established that all over the world among various branches of the food industry, the number of cases of food poisoning caused by public catering was the largest. To overcome this problem, the introduction of the HACCP system, as well as the standard and ISO 22000:2005 [34, 36–38] has a positive effect. In Taiwan, small and medium-sized food service enterprises have encountered a number of difficulties in implementing the HACCP system.

Studies of food enterprises in the east and west of Europe (Poland, Slovakia and Portugal) have established a positive impact on the implementation of food safety systems of the standard and ISO 22000:2005 on food safety and on the spread of food risks among the population [38].

In a comparative aspect, it was found that Lebanese catering enterprises in 2020 implemented ISO 22000:2005 (50 %), HACCP (40 %). Moreover, the ISO 22000:2005 standard was mainly implemented by large (85 %) and medium-sized (67 %) manufacturers, and only by small enterprises (29 %) [26].

We studied the impact of the HACCP (Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points) system in the food service industry in Greece and noted that ISO 22000:2005 is a valuable tool for food safety and contributes to enhancing the effect of the HACCP system and reducing the incidence of food poisoning. At the same time, it was noted that one of the biggest barriers to the implementation of ISO 22000:2005 and the HACCP system is the lack of understanding of these systems by staff, especially seasonal workers. Therefore, it is very important to improve their qualifications [30, 39].

In Spain, an important barrier to the use of a food safety system is that many food companies are not aware of its potential, but only note the high costs associated with its development. Since the implementation of food safety can lead to hazards at any stage of the food chain, proper control throughout the food chain is essential. Thus, food safety is ensured by the joint efforts of all parties involved in the food chain from feed producers and primary producers, food manufacturers, transport and storage operators and subcontractors to retailers [36, 40, 41]. All researchers unanimously agree that the HACCP system is one of the systematic preventive approaches that is used as a means of preventing the occurrence of food hazards, and not to check the finished product. Therefore, the correct and timely application of the HACCP system is very important. Since, according to the literature, most cases of food poisoning are associated with catering establishments, it is in these establishments that the introduction of the HACCP system is especially important.

3. 2. 1. HACCP system (Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point) and problems in its application in Ukraine

In Ukraine, the introduction of HACCP was started in 2002, but this process was plausible for operators of the food sector and therefore was not widespread and did not have state control. Large food exporting enterprises were the first to voluntarily introduce the HACCP system, since their products for export must be produced using this system [17, 19]. On September 20, 2016, Section VII of the Law of Ukraine “On the Basic Principles and Requirements for Safety and Quality of Food Products” came into force, which already stated that all food enterprises should have a HACCP system. A mandatory phased introduction of this system throughout the food sector was established over 3 years – until September 20, 2019. The first two stages of the implementation of the HACCP system concerned large and medium-sized enterprises. And by September 20, 2019, HACCP systems should have been introduced at small enterprises. There are significant penalties for non-compliance with this law.

Analyzing the first stage of HACCP implementation in the State Consumer Service of Ukraine, it was recognized that in 2017 the HACCP system was implemented only at 362 large enterprises, which accounted for only one third of all large enterprises, and two thirds of large enterprises did not comply with the law (HACCP was not implemented at 867 large enterprises) [42].

In 2019, the head of the State Food Service of Ukraine noted that, despite the established considerable fines, most enterprises fail, and some do not want to implement the HACCP system. In 2018, on average, 30–40 % of Ukrainian large and medium-sized food enterprises operated without using HACCP. Small producers during this period in 80–90 % of cases did not have a HACCP system.

In 2019–2020, 90 % of large enterprises have already implemented HACCP in Ukraine. More enterprises that have implemented this system are in Kharkiv region (82 % of the total number of enterprises), Dnipropetrovsk region – 73 %, and Vinnytsia region – 50 % [6, 19, 43]. So, the main problems in 2019–2020 regarding the implementation of legislative provisions on the mandatory implementation of the HACCP system are focused on medium and small enterprises. It was noted that the important problems in the implementation of the HACCP system are the lack of support for the management and personnel of the HACCP system, the insufficient level of qualification and knowledge of personnel in the field of HACCP, the economic situation in the country and the low level of income of the population [17, 19]. For the development of HACCP, technical competence and knowledge in the field of microbiology and food chemistry according to the HACCP methodology is important [16, 17]. Under such circumstances, when there is no competent staff, it is necessary to involve external experts, for which most small enterprises do not have the funds. The catering sector deserves special attention. In Ukraine, public catering (restaurants, bars, cafes, factory and student canteens, school and children's meals) fell into the third last period of HACCP implementation. This process took place more effectively in large restaurants because they had the resources, but it should be noted that not all large restaurants have implemented this system. Medium and small catering establishments are a big problem with the implementation of HACCP. These establishments are screened for HACCP, clarified, trained, and in some cases fined. At the same time, cases of food poisoning caused by the consumption of food in public catering establishments are often reported in the media [16, 17].

3. 3. The current state of the spread of food poisoning in Ukraine (retro analysis)

The official data on the spread of food poisoning in Ukraine were analyzed, namely, the number of outbreaks and the number of cases were determined. The results are shown in the **Tables 1, 2**.

Table 1

The number of outbreaks of food poisoning and the number of cases in 2019–2020

Indicators	2019	2020	% decrease in cases/person in 2020 compared to 2019
Number of outbreaks	204	52	25.48
Number of patients, including:	2,568	646	25.16
children	1,322	283	21.40
% of children sick in relation to the total number of sick	51.5	48.8	2.7

Data of **Table 1** shows that there was a trend to reduce the number of food poisoning in 2020 by an average of 21–25 %. In both 2019 and 2020, there is a significant number of children who have had food poisoning. In 2019, the percentage of children who fell ill in relation to the total number of people who had food poisoning was 51.5 %, and in 2020 – 48.8 %. These data confirm the general trend that children are particularly susceptible to foodborne pathogens.

Table 2 provides data on the number of outbreaks of food poisoning at the place of consumption of food.

Table 2 shows that in 2019, the most outbreaks of food poisoning were in public and school catering, which together accounted for 66.67 % of all reported cases of food poisoning that year, or 136 cases. Also, a significant number of poisonings were found in the private sector when people ate food at home. There were 45 or 22.06 % of such cases. **Table 2** also shows that in 2020, as in the previous 2019, the trend of a higher level of food poisoning in the catering sector continued – in canteens at factories, in cafes, restaurants, as well as in school meals compared to others analyzed cases. There were fewer cases of food poisoning both in 2019 and 2020 in preschool children's institutions. In 2020, there was a decrease in the number of food-related outbreaks compared to 2019. The main

sources of foodborne illness were the food consumed in schools and restaurants. In most cases, packaged food products and semi-finished products contributed to the poisoning. The two main bacterial foodborne disease classifications were *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella*.

Table 2

Relative and absolute indicators of the number of outbreaks of food poisoning in Ukraine by place of food in 2019–2020

Number of outbreaks, including:	2019		2020		% of cases in 2020 compared to 2019
	Number	%	Number	%	
	204	100	52	100	
Private sector	45	22.06	6	11.54	-13.33
Catering	78	38.24	23	44.23	-29.49
School meals	58	28.43	19	36.54	-32.76
Preschool	23	11.27	4	7.69	-17.39

According to official data, the main routes of transmission of food poisoning are: the process of food preparation – 27 outbreaks (51.9 %) in 2020 and 99 outbreaks (48.5 %) in 2019; contact – household route of transmission (contaminated hands, dishes, household items) – 14 outbreaks (26.9 %) in 2020 and 78 (38.2 %) in 2019. Violation of sanitary and anti-epidemic regimes, personal hygiene rules by children and the presence of staff/carriers among children and staff also contributed to outbreaks of the disease.

The distribution of food poisoning in different regions of Ukraine was also analyzed (**Fig. 1**)

Fig. 1. Number of outbreaks of food poisoning in different regions of Ukraine in 2019–2020

Fig. 1 shows that the number of cases of food poisoning was in most areas at the level of 12–23 % in relation to the total number of outbreaks. In Rivne and Ivano-Frankivsk, Odesa, Zaporizhzhia, Poltava regions in 2019, the number of cases was the highest.

Fig. 2 illustrates the indicators of the number of people who had food poisoning in different regions of Ukraine. So, in 2019, there were cases of mass poisoning in the Dnipropetrovsk region (25 factory workers in the factory canteen), in the Odesa region (41 people when eating shawarma, as well as 52 people, including 50 children in a sanatorium), Rivne region (48 people including 13 children in cafes), in the Zaporizhzhia region 4 outbreaks were recorded in the summer, in which 93 people were affected, including 17 children. The main reason is the use of home-made products purchased at spontaneous markets. In 2020, a case of food poisoning was registered in the Ivano-Frankivsk region, in which 194 factory workers who ate in the factory canteen were injured;

in the Rivne region, a case of mass poisoning in which 68 schoolchildren suffered while eating in the school cafeteria. The main causative agents of food poisoning were *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella*, the reproduction of which in food products was facilitated by non-compliance with sanitary requirements for personnel, cleaning of contact surfaces in catering departments and violation of requirements for the cold chain. The transmission of infectious agents occurred due to poor-quality food products, by household contact with the help of factors such as hands, dishes, household items (from untimely isolated sick (carriers) of children or staff), as well as with the use of poor-quality drinking water.

Fig. 2. The number of people who had food poisoning in different regions of Ukraine in 2019–2020

In 2020, the number of outbreaks was 55.34 % less, and the number of sick people during the year was 74.85 % less (2568 people in 2020 and 646 people in 2019).

It should be noted that a significant decrease in the number of outbreaks of food poisoning in 2020 is associated with the complete closure of catering establishments for a long period in connection with the implementation of anti-epidemic measures to prevent the spread of acute respiratory disease COVID-19 in Ukraine. Most cases of food poisoning are associated with eating in organized groups, especially in small catering establishments. One of the reasons for this is the lack of food safety control using such an effective tool as HACCP.

3. 4. Measures to improve the situation with the implementation of the food safety system – HACCP in Ukraine

As already noted in this article, catering establishments implemented the HACCP system at the very last stage after large and medium-sized food enterprises. This happened in September 2019. Therefore, at present, public catering enterprises are at the initial stage of mastering this system. The slowdown of this process was facilitated by flood restrictions, and currently the martial law in Ukraine. But still, in certain territories of Ukraine, where military actions are not taking place, it is necessary to introduce this system.

The HACCP system at all food enterprises, as well as at public catering enterprises (restaurants, cafes, bars, schools, kindergartens, etc.) is a mandatory requirement of the law. The HACCP system is the main lever for quality control of food products. It monitors critical points where risks or deviations from production standards are likely to occur. HACCP principles contribute to the protection of food products, from the inspection of raw materials to the delivery of products to the consumer. Thus, the HACCP system contributes to improving the safety and quality of products; reducing the number of state fines and increases the image value of the enterprise. The HACCP

system also reduces the risk of foodborne illness in consumers; improves employees' skills in food safety; improves control and overall management of the production process; provides full compliance with food safety standards.

First of all, what must be for the successful implementation of the HACCP system is to tune in to the effective implementation of this system, as well as to promote a culture of food safety among the staff. Management and staff should not be afraid of the HACCP system, it should be explained to them in very simple terms by consultants with vivid examples. Success in the fight against the spread of food poisoning depends primarily on effective modern legislation. Once the development of the HACCP system is approved in the enterprise, the best option for its successful implementation will be to invite a consultant who will organize the effective development of the system with the involvement of appropriate personnel in the working group. The development and implementation of the HACCP system should be carried out in accordance with its main seven principles. Legislation should promote safe food for the consumer, support food producers, and provide effective leverage for official inspection bodies in Ukraine.

In Ukraine, problems with HACCP in medium and small catering enterprises have the same features as in other countries, but the biggest problem is that this system was officially introduced for small and medium-sized enterprises in the food industry recently - only in September 2019 of the year. Prior to this, these companies were not checked by the state service for the presence of this system and did not know it. Almost two thirds of small and medium-sized enterprises have not yet been introduced in Ukraine HACCP. Large catering companies have mostly introduced this system. SMEs rushed to implement HACCP during this short period.

The low rate of implementation of the HACCP system lies in the fact that most small and medium-sized enterprises do not have the funds to implement it. Due to the lack of economic resources, most of them cannot allocate funds for consultants and modernization of catering facilities. This applies to school meals and meals in kindergartens, which are mostly state-owned and do not have funds for the HACCP system. Therefore, such companies are trying to independently develop HACCP, based on this system in another similar institution. This usually leads to many errors. Small and medium-sized enterprises face great difficulty in implementing these management systems due to the lack of sufficient qualifications, necessary competencies, financial resources and human resources.

Based on our experience in advising on the preparation of the HACCP development of the HACCP, it is possible to say that the success of the effectiveness of this system primarily depends on its understanding by the company's management and its desire to implement this system and effectively motivate the entire team to qualitatively comply with all requirements.

According to our observations, the main motivations for the introduction of the HACCP system by small and medium-sized enterprises were external legislative pressure for organizations to make the HACCP system mandatory, as well as the active participation of parents in schools and kindergartens and consumers who wanted to have guarantees of safe food for their children. The results of our observations identified three main limitations that hinder the effective implementation of the HACCP system in Ukraine in small and medium-sized enterprises - financial problems, fears of management that the system is very complex and will be difficult to implement, lack of specialists in organizations.

4. Conclusions

The state of the food legislation of Ukraine and its role in ensuring the safe nutrition of the population were analyzed, as well as the analysis of official data on food poisoning for 2019–2020 to establish trends. We assessed the current state of implementation of the HACCP system in the field of catering in Ukraine and analyzed the obstacles to the implementation of the HACCP system, which are used to achieve safe food. An analysis of the state of modern food legislation in Ukraine showed its very slow movement towards harmonization of EU requirements, and this led to a lag behind such developed countries as the USA and the EU in the implementation of the main legislative requirements to ensure food safety for the population by almost 20 years. Only at the end of 2019 in Ukraine there was an equal implementation of the law providing for the mandatory

implementation of the HACCP system by all enterprises in the food sector. This state of affairs contributed to the widespread spread of food poisoning among the population. In 2020, the number of outbreaks of food poisoning has dropped sharply, due to the hard lockdown, but they were still observed as a result of the use of the services of the population of small catering establishments, where the HACCP system has not yet been fully implemented.

According to official data, the HACCP system in small and medium-sized public catering establishments was implemented by an average of 55–65 % at the end of 2019. Outbreaks of food poisoning in 2019–2020 were in almost all regions of Ukraine, except for one – Chernihiv.

The level of outbreaks of food poisoning in Ukraine in 2020 decreased by an average of 25.5 % compared to the previous year. Such a sharp decrease in patients is due to the restriction of gatherings of large groups of people in catering in 2020, which was associated with the COVID-19 pandemic. This contributed to a significant reduction in the number of mass poisonings, when dozens of victims are recorded in each incident. In 2019, there were 13 mass food poisonings, and in 2020 – only 2 cases. In other cases of food poisoning, the victims were from 2 to 10 people in each incident.

The main products that contributed to the occurrence of food poisoning were cream confectionery, meat products and fish products. The cause of poisoning in most cases was *Salmonella* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, the reproduction of which in food products was facilitated by non-compliance with sanitary requirements for personnel, cleaning of contact surfaces in catering departments and violation of requirements for the cold chain.

The data presented in this article reinforce the understanding of the importance of the implementation of government measures such as legislation to ensure the safe nutrition of the population and public health, as well as the value of such a tool as HACCP in the prevention of food poisoning.

It has been determined that success in combating the spread of food poisoning depends on the effectiveness of food legislation, which should help ensure safe food for the consumer, support food producers and provide effective control levers to official inspection bodies (State Service of Ukraine of Food Safety and Consumer Protection) in Ukraine.

We have also confirmed that food safety and public health issues are inextricably linked to the fact that improperly processed food contributes to the occurrence of food poisoning, in particular for such a vulnerable population as children.

In 2020, the number of outbreaks of food poisoning was lower by an average of 21–25 %. This can be explained by the quarantine measures taken in Ukraine in connection with the coronavirus.

But the incidence of the population of Ukraine from the consumption of contaminated food is still high, including among children. The cause of poisoning in most cases was *Salmonella* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, the reproduction of which in food products was facilitated by non-compliance with sanitary requirements for personnel, cleaning of contact surfaces in catering departments and violation of requirements for the cold chain. This points to the importance of continued application of systemic preventive measures such as HACCP.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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